

HEREDITARY

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Deliverable 6.7

World Café Outcome: Priorities and Gaps

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101137074. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 6.7 describes the key priorities, gaps, and strategies for integrating multimodal health data and advancing sound health research, as emerged during the HEREDITARY World Café. The session was organized by the European Brain Council (EBC) in month 22 of the [HEREDITARY project](#), under Task 6.5 ‘Creating Policy Impact ‘Bridging Science, Policy and Society Training’’, within Work Package 6 ‘Citizen Science and Public Engagement’.

By gathering diverse stakeholder groups, including researchers, healthcare professionals, innovators, individuals with lived experiences, and patient organisation representatives, the World Café aimed to foster mutual learning, empower participants to share their insights on existing priorities in neuroscience research, identify actionable strategies to overcome gaps, and contribute to informing brain health policy decisions.

Looking forward, as leaders of Task 6.5, EBC intends to continue promoting such a participative approach to research, amplifying EU brain community voices and helping shape policy decisions grounded in evidence-based knowledge.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable ID	D6.7
Deliverable Title	World Café Outcome: Priorities and Gaps
Work Package	WP6
Lead Partner	European Brain Council
Due date	31/12/2025
Date of submission	23/12/2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

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REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	21/11/2025	Laura Guiso	First draft
0.2	03/12/2025	Eugenia Cornide	Reviewed first draft
0.3	12/12/2025	Laura Guiso	Second draft integrating comments
1.0	17/12/2025	Anna Romanovych	Finalisation of the layout

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1 INTRODUCTION

Harnessing Artificial Intelligence (AI) to analyse and integrate multimodal health data, or health data stemming from different sources and formats, including medical imaging, genomic, and environmental data, offers a more holistic understanding of complex diseases. By leveraging AI and advanced analytics to integrate multimodal health data, the [HEREDITARY project](#) - a four-year, EU-funded initiative coordinated by Università degli Studi di Padova (UNIPD) - seeks to better understand the risk factors and treatment responses of neurodegenerative and gut-brain axis related disorders for better care. The project targets all actors of the health research field, including researchers, clinicians, policymakers, but also citizens and the broader public, to advance more inclusive and effective brain health research. Using secure supercomputer environments to facilitate federated learning, the project ensures sensitive health data is stored and analysed safely, in compliance with regulatory requirements.

Leading Task 6.5 ‘Creating Policy Impact ‘Bridging Science, Policy and Society Training’’, the European Brain Council (EBC) organized a HEREDITARY World Café to leverage the voices of the EU brain community and jointly address future health priorities and gaps. The aim of the event was to gather diverse stakeholder perspectives to explore practical solutions to challenges in multimodal health data research and propose policy-relevant solutions to inform brain health policy decisions.

Conducted under Work Package 6 (WP6), ‘Citizen Science and Public Engagement’, led by OBSERVA, the activity reinforced the project’s citizen-science approach by promoting the public’s active participation in research processes. By engaging individuals with lived experience, policymakers, healthcare providers, patient association representatives in the discussions, the HEREDITARY World Café extended WP6’s participative research approach to foster collaboration between scientific stakeholders and relevant actors in the research field, to support evidence-based brain health policy development.

2 METHODOLOGY

Held on the morning of October 16, 2025, as a side event of EBC's Brain Innovation Days (BIDays), the HEREDITARY World Café brought together sixteen participants representing innovators, patient organisation representatives, researchers, individuals with lived experiences, and healthcare professionals.

Participants were invited to the World Café via targeted e-mail outreach, selected based on their roles and expertise relevant to the HEREDITARY project's key topics. When registering for the event, participants provided consent for photographs to be publicly shared. By assigning roles to each confirmed participant, EBC ensured diversity in stakeholder representation and a balanced distribution across stakeholder groups. Gender balance was also considered: of the sixteen participants, seven were females and nine were males, distributed between two discussion tables of nearly equal size.

Each table was facilitated by an EBC team-member acting as both a moderator and a note-taker, responsible for taking track of time, ensuring participants had equal opportunities to voice their opinions, and that the discussions remained pertinent to the questions designed. To guarantee balanced representation, labelled name cards were used to assign participants from each stakeholder group, innovators, patient organisation representatives, researchers, individuals with lived experiences, and healthcare professionals, to both tables. By so doing, different perspectives mixed, shaped by participants' varied expertise in HEREDITARY's main themes, namely, AI, health data integration, privacy and security, neurodegenerative and gut microbiome-related disorders.

Discussion questions were developed ahead of the event, drawing on key challenges in multimodal health data integration identified by the HEREDITARY consortium and by related projects involved in Task 8.4's 'Liaison with related projects and initiatives' activities. Five questions structured the session, with roughly fifteen minutes of discussion allocated for each. Below, the discussion questions:

- 1) *How can we better integrate diverse health data sources—like electronic health records, genomics, wearables, environmental exposures, and patient-reported outcomes—to drive more precise, effective, and inclusive care?*
- 2) *What strategies are needed to ensure health data collection is high-quality, representative, and inclusive across all populations and care settings?*
- 3) *How can cross-sector collaboration—between academia, industry, public institutions and society—be strengthened to accelerate the translation of brain and health research into scalable, real-world solutions?*
- 4) *How can we design AI-powered health tools that are clinically meaningful, user-friendly, and aligned with both patient and clinician needs—while ensuring ethical, explainable, and biologically valid outcomes?*
- 5) *How can the EU balance strong data protection regulations—like GDPR and the European Health Data Space—with the need to enable timely, life-saving medical research and innovation?*

Upon arrival, participants were welcomed into an informal, comfortable setting with coffee and tea, and seating arranged according to stakeholder group labels. The disposition of the room encouraged participant interaction and dialogue. The session

spanned an hour and fifteen minutes, with the discussions preceded by an introduction to the HEREDITARY project, the session's aim and methodology, and concluding with closing remarks, thanking participants and acknowledging their contributions.

Later in the day, Giuseppe Pellegrini, professor at the University of Trento and president of OBSERVA, presented a summary of the HEREDITARY World Café's key insights, during the "HEREDITARY World Café Wrap-up" session on the BIDays main stage.

The following sections of the report are organized by discussion question and outline proposed solutions to key priorities and gaps in multimodal health data integration research. Contributions reflect the perspectives of innovators, representatives of patient organizations, researchers, individuals with lived experience, and healthcare professionals, and are summarized in the report's conclusion.

3 PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS TO CHALLENGES IN MULTIMODAL HEALTH DATA RESEARCH

3.1 How can we better integrate diverse health data sources—like electronic health records, genomics, wearables, environmental exposures, and patient-reported outcomes—to drive more precise, effective, and inclusive care?

To better integrate multimodal health data, three main potential solutions were identified, namely the need to: establish European standards on data standardization, teach both researchers and healthcare professionals about data standardization methods, and, finally, incentivize adherence to FAIR data principles.

Data standardization refers to the process of organizing multimodal data into a uniform, predefined format and structure to improve, for example, data quality, data integration and reusability, and collaborative research. Clinical health data often presents inconsistencies in both format and structure across healthcare systems and hospitals, resulting in batch effects and potential inaccurate conclusions. Almost all HEREDITARY World Café stakeholder groups agreed that setting European standards for data standardization would help create consistency across pilot and clinical protocols, reducing batch effects, or variations in data associated to technical factors such as processing samples at different times or locations, using different equipment, as well as possible inaccurate conclusions. Defining Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) was identified as a means to establish such data standardization guidelines to correct health data collection and data analysis methods. One participant referred to the Human Phenotype Morphology (HPO), a standardized vocabulary of phenotypic abnormalities, as a tangible example of how data standardization guidelines are possible and effective. However, as another participant pointed out, while data minimization (the data privacy and protection principle by which one should be selective about the type of personal information collected, processed, and time such data is stored for) is fundamental in integrating health data, it also presents challenges. Specifically, only some types of data can be collected and processed, and for a short amount of time, limiting the availability of long-term health data. For the above reasons, considering the temporal aspect of data minimization, collecting longitudinal health data could help advance health research and innovation.

The second solution that emerged from the discussions for combining health data from multiple sources is to provide training for healthcare professionals and researchers in data annotation, documentation, and analysis. While data standardization is frequently discussed, the practicalities of it are often unknown. Therefore, investing in training on data standardization would help spread knowledge on how to enhance data quality, analysis and accessibility, ultimately improving precision in data, and hence advancing sound health research. Additionally, to incentivize data standardization knowledge, highlighting its relevant contribution to health research in the long term might be a potential strategy to facilitate multimodal health data integration.

Finally, there was common agreement among participants on the need to promote interactive and interoperable data and adherence to [FAIR Guiding Principles](#) to better integrate multimodal health data. More broadly, the discussion highlighted the need to optimise data reusability, one of the core objectives of FAIR data principles, which aim

to make research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The upside, as noted by one participant, is that significant innovation on data security protocols, privacy, and interoperability is underway, reflecting notable progress towards the harmonization of multimodal health data.

Figure 1 – Photograph showing the HEREDITARY World Café participants engaging in discussions

3.2 What strategies are needed to ensure health data collection is high-quality, representative, and inclusive across all populations and care settings?

Creating cross-border collaboration, raising awareness of diverse populations, establishing trust, and adopting a co-creation research approach were discussed as key strategies to achieve greater representation and inclusion in health data collection across populations and care settings. To further support these goals, participants highlighted the need for a shared definition of data inclusivity and increased funding for health research. Such efforts would enhance data standardization, resulting in more consistent, uniform, and higher-quality data.

Participants agreed that fostering cross-border collaboration with regions such as Africa and Asia, could help improve data representativeness - namely through patient engagement in EU-project proposal calls and synergies with global associations. Raising awareness of underrepresented populations, mapping such populations, and examining the generalizations made in health data studies were considered essential to strengthen the validity of research outcomes. One patient advocate illustrated the latter issue using clinical work with male rats versus female rats to exemplify the lack of health data representativity and erroneous generalized conclusions. Essentially, many studies test on male rats to simplify data processes and reduce costs. However, this practice leads

to conclusions which cannot be applied to the broader population. Collecting representative data is important; but equally important is clarifying that the data collected is not representative and explicitly mentioning this in research findings.

Establishing trust among populations that are reluctant to share health data requires transparency about how data will be used, and robust assurances that it will be stored and analysed securely. Participants agreed that research should be developed with patients, for patients, and emphasized the importance of reflecting on the tools and processes used in studies. The language of the calls for research study invitations, for example, is significant to foster truly inclusive stakeholder engagement.

Defining what data inclusivity means was seen as important for all stakeholders involved in the discussions – researchers, innovators, healthcare professionals, patient organisation representatives, and individuals with lived experiences alike. One innovator noted that there is an unspoken agreement on what equitable, representative, and diverse data means: although terms like equitable, representative, and diverse data are widely used, their meanings vary across contexts. Developing clearer guidelines on which standards and sources to follow was considered an important step toward ensuring that collected data are indeed inclusive.

Finally, all World Café participants agreed that inclusive and representative health data are essential to advancing effective health solutions. However, such health data is often costly to collect. Therefore, increasing funding would allow for long-term clinical study grants and investment in higher-quality data collection and analysis tools, improving the quality and duration of research, and contributing to more representative health data overall.

Figure 2 – Photograph showing the HEREDITARY World Café participants engaging in discussions

3.3 How can cross-sector collaboration—between academia, industry, public institutions and society—be strengthened to accelerate the translation of brain and health research into scalable, real-world solutions?

Participants agreed that cross-sectoral collaboration is key to accelerate the translation of brain and health research into practical solutions. There was common consensus on the need for all stakeholders, including policymakers, to collaborate and share research perspectives. However, at the same time, participants equally acknowledged that achieving such a cooperation remains challenging. Building on earlier discussions around representative data collection, participants highlighted cross-border partnerships with Africa and Asia, the inclusion of patient advocates, and stronger alignment with global associations as key approaches to advancing cross-sector collaboration.

Figure 3 – Photograph showing the HEREDITARY World Café participants engaging in discussions

3.4 How can we design AI-powered health tools that are clinically meaningful, user-friendly, and aligned with both patient and clinician needs—while ensuring ethical, explainable, and biologically valid outcomes?

The discussion started with broad consensus that AI is advancing health research and innovation, and, for this reason, that its progress should not be hindered but carefully monitored. While AI proves very useful, its work must be verified and validated by qualified experts. To develop user-friendly, needs-based AI-tools, a proposed strategy was to implement at-home devices to record patient conversations, as opposed to solely relying on administering questionnaires. Such an approach would, however, require

secure data storage and strict protocols to ensure that data is shared only with the consent of the patient.

Both patient advocates and researchers argued about the potential of AI tools to capture health data from everyday life, such as through sensors for eye movement, speech, walking, and so on. Such health data could then be integrated with historical health data records, to enrich datasets and include a wider range of health determinants. AI-powered health tools could also enhance health data security and help safeguard patients' privacy rights. However, researchers and patient advocates pointed out that unequal access to advanced technology may result in underrepresentation of disadvantaged populations in health data samples. Therefore, it is crucial not only to empower individuals by improving digital and health literacy, but also to explore alternative methods for engaging and collecting data from those less familiar with or less exposed to advanced technologies.

Lastly, when deploying AI-powered tools to advance health research, questions on the volume and sources of data collected must be raised and reflected upon, to avoid gathering unnecessary, costly, or trivial information.

3.5 How can the EU balance strong data protection regulations—like GDPR and the European Health Data Space—with the need to enable timely, life-saving medical research and innovation?

The [European Health Data Space Regulation \(EHDS\)](#) was entered into force in March 2025 as part of the EU's efforts to establish a common framework for the use and exchange of secure electronic health data across EU member states. Among other relevant EU frameworks, the EDHS builds on the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#), a data privacy law adopted in May 2016, that defines the obligations to protect EU citizens' personal data and to ensure the free movement of such data within the EU. Altogether, both regulations are fundamental to governing how personal data can be collected, processed, analysed, and transferred. However, to strike an effective balance between stringent data protection regulations and the advancement of life-saving medical research and innovation within the EU, participants agreed that the key lies in finding a middle ground. Such a balance involves safeguarding individuals' privacy without imposing overly restrictive measures from a scientific perspective.

The strategies identified by participants include creating a streamlined, EU-level health data platform that minimizes bureaucratic hurdles, encourages data standardization, and prevents the collection of low-quality health data. Another strategy to enable timely innovation raised by a researcher concerns the reduction of the time for ethical approval processes, which is often prolonged by GDPR-related requirements. Indeed, it was noted that for EU research studies, it usually takes over a year to obtain ethical approval, hence slowing down the innovation process by significantly delaying study timelines. By shortening the waiting times and building greater trust in the capacity to store data safely, health research and innovation could be markedly accelerated.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the HEREDITARY World Café, an EBC-led activity under the project’s WP6, Task 6.5, took place in the morning of 16 October 2025. The objective was to bring together diverse stakeholders active in health research - innovators, patient organisation representatives, researchers, individuals with lived experiences, and healthcare professionals - to discuss solutions to challenges identified in harnessing multimodal health data integration and to drive policy impact in brain research. Moving forward, the insights gained from these discussions can serve as a foundation for developing data standards and educational programs, building trust between the scientific community and society, and enhancing public participation in scientific research initiatives.

As highlighted by one of the World Café participants, harmonizing health data is an investment both in terms of time and finances. Therefore, reflecting throughout the research process on why data is being harmonised and how the data will be used afterwards is key to assessing whether one’s research is moving in the right direction. Fostering such conversations and reflective approaches is crucial to advancing health research, as they allow priorities, gaps, and strategies in health research to be identified and improved.

Summarised below in a table format are some of the key priorities, gaps, and corresponding strategies identified by the sixteen World Café participants in leveraging multimodal health data research to advance understanding of disease risk factors, causes, and treatments.

Table 1 – Overview of proposed solutions to challenges in multimodal health data integration identified by the HEREDITARY World Café participants

Key Discussion Area	Summary of Insights and Recommendations
Data quality and data standardization	Participants stressed the need for data standardization and the collection of high-quality, usable data. Suggested strategies included the development of common standardized clinical protocols for data acquisition and analysis, as well as providing education and training for healthcare professionals on required data elements.
Patient empowerment and inclusion	The discussion emphasized empowering patients in data sharing consent processes, building awareness and trust among underrepresented populations, and fostering cross-sectoral collaboration. Participants also highlighted the importance of promoting cross-border cooperation, the need to clearly define what is meant by data representation and inclusion, and to remain attentive about batch effects to avoid overgeneralisation of findings.
AI-powered tools in data collection	AI-driven tools were recognized as valuable for collecting user-friendly, clinically meaningful data, to record everyday life movements and home-based data.

Key Discussion Area	Summary of Insights and Recommendations
	However, participants emphasized the need to uphold individuals' data privacy rights, improve health and digital literacy, and explore alternative methods to engage individuals who are less exposed to and/or less familiar with advanced technologies.
EU data protection and regulation	Participants noted that strict EU data protection regulations can sometimes hinder research and data collection processes. It was suggested that the EU should simplify and reduce bureaucratic barriers within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) to facilitate data protection processes to advance medical research and innovation.